

Universal Xalqaro Ilmiy Jurnal

Jurnalning bosh sahifasi: <https://universaljurnal.uz>

Universal International Scientific Journal

e-ISSN: [3060-4540 \(online\)](https://doi.org/10.30604/5440)

Year: 2024 Issue: 1 Volume: 7

Published: 3.10.2024 <https://universaljurnal.uz>

International indexes

GOOGLE SCHOLAR

CROSSREF (OAK BAZA)

ZENODO

OPEN AIRE

EUROPUB

RESEARCHGATE (OAK BAZA)

SJIF

Muqimova Zilolabonu Davronbek kizi

Andijan State University

Uzbekistan

zilolamuqimova28@gmail.com

BONES – OSTEOLOGY

Abstract: 1.5 - 1.7 parts of the human body consists of bones. a set of bones is called a skeleton. The Greek word for skeleton is skeleton. based on the word, it means "dried". Such a meaning The reason for its inclusion is that in ancient times the skeleton was affected by the heat of the sun or sand. Made with a skeleton one is an odd number. Conventionally, the skeleton is divided into 2 parts - the axis skeleton and the appendage. skeletonized. Skull skeleton (23 bones), chest (37 bones), including the spine (33-34 bones). Additional skeletal structure includes: arm skeleton (64), leg skeleton (62).

Key words: Osteology, Abu Ali ibn Sina, osteocytes, osteoclasts, osteoblasts, . bones in the body, skull bones, bones of the shoulder girdle, bones of the arm, pelvic bones.

Annotatsiya: Inson tanasining 1,5-1,7 qismi suyaklardan iborat. suyaklar to'plamiga skelet deyiladi. Yunoncha skelet so'zi skelet.so'zga asoslanib, bu "quritilgan"degan ma'noni anglatadi. Bunday ma'no uning kiritilishining sababi shundaki, qadimgi davrlarda skeletga quyosh yoki qum issiqligi ta'sir qilgan. Skelet bilan qilingan toq son. An'anaviy ravishda skelet 2 qismga bo'linadi-eksa skeleti va qo'shimchasi. skeletlangan. Bosh suyagi skeleti (23 suyak), ko'krak qafasi (37 suyak), shu jumladan umurtqa pog'onasi (33-34 suyak). Qo'shimcha skelet tuzilishiga quyidagilar kiradi: qo'l skeleti (64), oyoq skeleti (62).

Kalit so'zlar: osteologiya, Abu Ali ibn Sino, osteotsitlar, osteoklastlar, osteoblastlar, tanadagi suyaklar, bosh suyagi suyaklari, elkama-kamar suyaklari, qo'l suyaklari, tos suyaklari.

Аннотация: 1,5 - 1,7 части человеческого тела состоят из костей. набор костей называется скелетом. Греческое слово, обозначающее скелет, - skeleton. В переводе с греческого оно означает "высушенный". Такое значение объясняется тем, что в древние времена скелет подвергался воздействию солнечного тепла или песка. Число скелетов, изготовленных из единицы, является нечетным. Традиционно скелет делится на 2 части - осевой скелет и придаток. скелетонизированный. Скелет черепа (23 кости), грудной клетки (37 костей), включая позвоночник (33-34 кости). Дополнительная структура скелета включает в себя: скелет руки (64), скелет ноги (62).

Ключевые слова: остеология, Абу Али ибн Сина, остециты, остеокласты, остеобласты, кости тела, кости черепа, кости плечевого пояса, кости руки, кости таза.

Language: English

Citation: Муқимова , Z. BONES – OSTEOLOGY. *Universal International Scientific Journal*, 1(7), 28–31. Retrieved from <https://universaljurnal.uz/index.php/jurnal/article/view/1155>

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13981915>

One of the main functions of the human body is its ability to move. This movement occurs with the participation of bones and muscles. The musculoskeletal system consists of the active moving part - muscles, and the inactive part - the bones and ligaments that connect them. The musculoskeletal system is the main part of the body (72.5% of the total body weight). The skeletal system accounts for 10% in men and 8.5% in women. The average weight of bones is 5-6 kg.

Osteology - studies the structure of bones. The body is difficult the set of bones forming the basis is the skeleton. Skeleton (Greek skeletos) is derived from the word dried. While describing the spine, Ibn Sina clearly mentioned the number of scholars, and the functions of the spine fully correspond to modern concepts. He also identified the differences between the spines. While Aristotle stated that there are 8 ribs, Ibn Sina was the first to write that a person has 12 pairs of ribs, and the number of ribs is the same in

men and women. Until the 10th century, there was no clear idea about the structure of the pelvic bones. Rufus described the pelvic bone as a pelvic joint, Pollux described it as a flat bony bulge, Hippocrates understood the hip bone by this term, Abu Ali ibn Sina was the first in the world to accurately describe the structure of the pelvic bones. The human skeleton consists of more than 206 individual bones. 85 of them are equal. The weight of the skeleton is 5-6 kg, in men it is 10% of the total body weight, in women it is 8.5%. In the human embryo, bone tissue develops later than other tissues, in the middle of the second month of life in the mother's womb, from individual cells - osteoblasts - that are formed from the mesenchyme. These osteoblasts produce intermediate bone substances that fulfill the function of support. All bones do not develop in the same way during development, some of them (cranial and facial bones) develop from connective tissue or go through two stages. These are called bones. Bone tissue, like other skeletal tissues, mainly

consists of bone cells - osteocytes, osteoclasts, osteoblasts and intercellular osseous substance. The intermediate substance consists of osteogenic fibers (similar to collagen fibers) and the main substance. If we look at the cross-section of a normal bone under a microscope, we can see its structures consisting of osteons of different shapes and sizes. Osteons are located differently depending on the function of the bones. In smooth long bones, they are located along the length of the bones, in hollow bones from above to the right, and in straight and flat bones, they are parallel to the bone surface. Osteon and Haver's system refer to the collection of bony plates surrounding blood vessels. 5-15 bone plates can be placed around each blood vessel. The hardness of bones depends on the structure of the bone plates and the composition of the intermediate substance. Bone cartilage is an amorphous substance rich in ossein (collagen) fibers and mineral salts, as well as bone cells. The fibers in rubber are usually parallel to each other and oriented in the same direction.

They include the skull, facial bones and spine; other bones go through three stages (rard, ankle, bone) and are called secondary bones. The skeleton performs musculoskeletal, protective and biological functions.

1. The support function is formed by the attachment of soft tissues and organs to some parts of the skeleton.

2. The skill of movement is manifested by the formation of various handles of the bones that make up the skeleton, and their connection through the joints and contraction of muscles with the help of the nervous system.

3. The protective function arose from separate parts of the skeleton

spaces are used. For example, the spinal canal is the spinal cord, the bones of the skull protects the brain, chest, lungs and heart from external influences.

4. The biological function of suyardar is a large amount of minerals

calcium, phosphorus, magnesium and other elements involved in metabolism

In addition, the red marrow located in the epiphyses of the bones produces blood elements that act as biological protection in the body. In the skeleton, the head, body, arms and legs are distinguished. The function of the shape of the bones related to according to the development, structure and function of bones divided into the following types: 1. Tubular bones can be long or short. Tubular bones have two widened ends - epiphyses, and are located in the middle has a tube-shaped body or diaphysis. Located relatively close to the body the end of the bone is the proximal epiphysis, the expanded end located farther from the body -called the distal epiphysis. The part of the bone between the epiphysis and the diaphysis called the metaphysis. The long bones include the palmar bones of the paws, the phalanges of the fingers enters. The long bones of the tubular bones are the shoulder, hip, shoulder blade, and tibia includes bones. From the short tubular bones, the palmar bones of the hand and foot, finger phalanges are formed. Diaphyseal parts of bones are made of dense bone, and the epiphyses are made of porous bone and a dense substance with a thin layer on top of it covers 2. The pore is covered with a dense substance over the bones, and the pore is inside substance is located. Porous substance without irregular arrangement of bone structures, resistance to compressive forces located in a certain direction, in the form

of arcs able to show and carry large loads. Like and the metatarsal bones of the foot, vertebral bodies, sesamoid bones are porous enters the bones. Sesamoid bones meet near joints and muscles can be located in the tendons. Patellar cap to the largest sesamoid bone enters. 3. Flat bones are involved in the delimitation of spaces, such as the skull provides formation of the skeleton, chest, and pelvic cavities. Flat the two outer plates of bones are made of dense material, the layer between the plates and it is made of thin porous material. Flat bones in the skull skeleton pore material is called diploe. Flat bones include shoulder, pelvic girdle, sternum and includes the bones of the cranial skeleton covering the part of the brain. 4. Spherical the bodies of bones are cavities filled with air, and the surface of the cavities is mucous covered with a curtain. This structure of the bone is the strength of the bone without breaking it, greatly lightens its mass. The skeleton of the skull is spherical bone, upper jaw, forehead bone, sphenoid bone to the type of gular bones

enters. 5. Mixed type bones have a complex shape and several consists of parts. The origin, structure and shape of the parts that make up the bone differ from each other.

Bone types: According to the location of the human skeleton, it is divided into the following groups:

1. Bones in the body: vertebrae, ribs, sternum.
2. Skull bones: facial bones, brain box bones.
3. Bones of the shoulder girdle: scapula, vertebral bone.
4. Bones of the arm: bones of the shoulder, elbow, wrist and hand.
5. Pelvic bones.
6. Leg bones: femur, tibia, tibia and leg bones. Bones are composed of 70% inorganic (50% water) and 30% organic (16% fat) substances. Defatted bone is 1/3 organic and 2/3 inorganic.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Netter's Atlas of human Anatomy
2. Atlas of Anatomy Volume Sobotta
3. <https://www.visiblebody.com>
4. <https://en.wikipedia.org>
5. <https://byjus.com>
6. <https://www.urmc.rochester.edu>